

Complexes of Uranium (VI) and Thorium (IV) with 2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl-Acetophenone

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The reactions of 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone with uranium (VI) and thorium (IV) have been studied by both conductometric and spectrophotometric methods. In acidic medium, uranyl ions develop instantaneously orange colour while thorium ions, yellow colour with this reagent. The colour intensity remains unchanged even on keeping for a week or so. Temperature variations up to 80° have no effect. Vosburgh and Cooper's method, Job's method of continued variation and slope ratio method show that reagent forms only 2 : 1 complex with uranium only while 1 : 1 with thorium. The values of stability constants of uranium and thorium complexes are calculated to be 1.4×10^7 and 2.66×10^2 (or $-\Delta F^\circ$'s of 9.91 Kcal and 3.35 Kcal/mol. respectively) at 30° respectively.

The metal complexes of aromatic hydroxy aldehydes and ketones have mainly been used for the detection and estimation of these metals. For example, the insoluble complexes of copper, nickel and ferric ion with salicylaldehyde¹ have been used for gravimetric estimation of these metals. Another aldehyde namely, pyrogallol aldehyde^{2,3} has been employed for the colorimetric detection of thorium and zirconium.

Amongst the aromatic hydroxy ketones, 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone has been used for the colorimetric detection of iron⁴ and boron⁵.

Little attention has, however, been paid to the study of the composition, stability and structure of the complexes of these compounds. The complexes which have been studied potentiometrically by Wilson and Calvin^{6,7}, are those of copper, nickel and zinc with salicylaldehyde and its derivatives.

No work on the reactions of metals with 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone (H.M.A.) is reported in the existing literature. The present investigations are aimed at to determine the composition and stability of uranium (VI) and thorium (IV) complexes with H.M.A. The reagent develops an orange colour with uranyl ions and yellow with thorium ions. The reactions are instantaneous. The solutions are highly stable and their colour intensity

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remains unchanged even on keeping for a week or so, temperature variations upto 80° have no effect on their colour intensity.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of H.M.A.: The phenone was prepared by Fries migration⁸ of *p*-cresyl acetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The product was crystallized from alcohol when yellow needle like crystals (m.p. 50°) were obtained. Its solution was prepared in 50% alcohol.

Apparatus: A unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 500, was used for absorbance measurements.

pH measurements were made with Beckman pH-meter, model H. The conductivity measurements were made with the help of Philip's (PR9500) conductivity bridge.

Uranium-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone complex: The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁹ was employed to determine the nature and the number of complexes present in the orange solution. The absorbance of solutions of uranyl nitrate and the reagent ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 were measured over wide spectral range. The reagent solution was used as blank. All these solutions exhibited the maximum absorption at 380 m μ showing the formation of only one complex.

Influence of pH on stability of the complex: The complex was found to be stable in the pH range 3.0–4.5. Above pH 4.5, the complex got hydrolysed resulting in the precipitation of uranium hydroxide. The complex attained maximum colour intensity at pH 4.0.

Composition of the complex: Job's method of continued variation¹⁰ was employed to determine the composition of the complex. The method showed that complex contains uranium and the reagent in the ratio 1 : 2. The conductometric titrations of uranyl nitrate against the reagent also showed the existence of 1 : 2 complex.

Evaluation of stability constants: The stability constant K of the complex was determined by the modified Anderson method as adopted by Dey and Coworkers¹¹. Since the uranyl ions have no absorbance at 380 m μ (λ_{\max} of the complex), hence the absorbance of the solution may be due to the reagent and the coloured complex. In the descending portion of the curves (Fig. 1) where the uranyl ions are in excess, it may be safely assumed that the reagent is fully complexed with uranyl ions and does not contribute to the colour of the solution; hence the absorbance of the solution is due to the coloured complex alone. Taking into account of these assumptions, the value of K was calculated to be 1.49×10^7 . The free energy of formation was also determined from the relationship $-\Delta F^\circ = RT \log K$ and its value was found to be 9.91 Kcals/mol. at 30°.

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FIG 1
 CURVE 1. CONCENTRATION OF THE REACTANTS = $8 \times 10^{-3} M$.
 CURVE 2. CONCENTRATION OF THE REACTANTS = $4 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Structure of the complex: Assuming that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the uranyl ion which in turn is coordinated through the carbonyl oxygen, the structure of the complex may be written as :

UO_2 -2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone.

Thorium-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone complex: Application of Vosburgh and Cooper's method demonstrated the formation of only one complex having maximum absorption at $375 m\mu$. The complex was found to be stable in the pH range 2.5-4.5 and attained maximum colour intensity at pH 3.5. Job's method performed at $375 m\mu$ showed the formation of 1 : 1 complex.

In slope ratio method¹², the concentration of the variable component was varied from $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $3.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ in the presence of fixed concentration ($8 \times 10^{-4} M$ in 25 ml.) of the other component. The ratio of the slopes of plots of absorbance at $375 m\mu$ vs. concentration of the variable component confirms the existence of 1 : 1 complex.

The conductometric titrations further confirmed its composition as 1 : 1.

The stability constant of the complex was found to be 2.62×10^2 while $-\Delta F^\circ$ 3.35 Kcals/mole at 30° .

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The complex may be represented by the following structure.

Thorium (IV)-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone.

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